

INTERFERENCE IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES)

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Annotation

This article deals with the problem of interference between two languages as Uzbek and English. The grammatical and lexical differences had been analyzed in the topic. Furthermore, positive and negative effects of interference on the language had been discussed.

Key words: interference, aspect, communication, unit, bilingualism, structure, spelling, pronunciation.

Due to globalization and technological development of the world, almost every person is in an atmosphere of multilingualism when he does not only have to deal with different languages besides your native one, but you also have to use different languages depending on the communication situation. All these contacting languages inevitably influence each other as at the level of individual use and globally, at the societal level. This is not so much about mixing languages, i.e. simultaneous use of lexical units of different languages, namely about the unconscious transfer of structural norms and systems of one language to norms of another, which leads to violations of the norms of the second language and in that or some other degree of imperfect possession. In conditions of bilingualism phenomenon is expressed in the influence of the prevailing, native language on all other studied languages are called "interference".

Furthermore, L.V. Shcherba spoke about the deforming influence of the first language when learning other languages, although the term "interference" appeared much later. In modern science, the term "interference" means interaction of language systems in conditions of bilingualism or multilingualism. Many scientists are unanimous in the opinion that the effect of interference has only a negative result, and this is a process of deviation from the norm contacting languages, changes in the structure and elements of languages under influence of each other. Moreover, this process is considered to be in two-way, since there is an influence on both the native language and the foreign language and vice versa. For example, given the colossal role of English language in the modern world, it is recognized that it also provokes changes in the use of other languages and in some cases becomes a leader language even over the native one, determining its use person.

In science, various types of interference are distinguished depending on the language level. In this article we will focus on interference in the most susceptible to change aspects of language – interference in vocabulary and grammar, which determine the process of speech production and communications in any language. In particular, at the lexical level the vocabularies of two languages merge into a single lexical fund and concepts are introduced into one language from another, in other words, this is the intervention of the vocabulary of one language system into another. Borrowed vocabulary can initially be equally used together with old vocabulary, but in the future either completely replaces the old word, or acquires a highly specialized meaning, provided that both words are preserved in the language. Also while preserving both old and new concepts, they can be divided according to style and sphere of use, for example, newcomer words can acquire the status of refined, sublime, or, conversely, appear on the list

of jargon or elements of vulgar speech. However, the process of borrowing new words from other languages (now most often from English) occurs uncontrollably, almost chaotically and without human participation, so now the problem is becoming more acute excessive introduction of English vocabulary into the Uzbek language. Besides Anglicisms come to the Uzbek language along with their grammatical characteristics in terms of gender, number, combination with a verb, etc. most influence the use of “neighboring” Uzbek words and the construction statements.

Another aspect of lexical interference is the so-called “false friends of the translator”, when translating from English it is used the meaning that comes to mind by association with the Uzbek language. “False friends of the translator” are a pair of words in two languages that are similar in spelling and/or pronunciation, but different in meaning. There are a large number of such pairs both between Uzbek and English. Let us look at some examples of pairs of false friends of a translator in Uzbek, English in tables 1:

Examples of pairs of “translator’s false friends «in English and Uzbek languages

False friend	False translation (Uzbek)
Abstract	Abstrakt
Replica	Replika
Fabric	Fabrika
Anecdote	Anikdot
Physician	Fizik

Table 1

“The translator’s false friends” only superficially resemble acquaintances lexemes are in their native language, so when working with them in another language it is necessary to clarify their meaning in the dictionary in order to avoid incorrect use of meaning.

Another type of interference affecting the use of the second language – grammatical interference. Grammatical interference arises when the rules of application, coordination of grammatical structures of one language instinctively applied to approximately the same chains of elements of another language, which also leads to a violation of the norms of this language. This is how rules and stable rules are imposed forms from Uzbek into English or transfer rules of the English language for all subsequent languages studied. For example, in Uzbek is agglutinative and the sentence are temporal, spatial, causal, investigative and other relations are expressed more often by suffixes. In English, these relationships are expressed only by prepositions. Moreover, there are no prepositions in Uzbek and English languages often does not match. Also in Uzbek, and English words differ in the categories of gender, number and case. Often come from a deviation from the norms when translating such nouns that combine with verbs only in the singular or plural, but used in a different number in the target language. Difficulties arise and due to the absence of many categories in the system of any language, for example, due to the lack of an article category in the Uzbek language, all students of English have problems with this problem. Many other grammatical categories of the Uzbek language also cause difficulties. This primarily concerns verbs, since they were learned from childhood by native Uzbek speakers and are used they automatically and unconsciously in speech, as well as in the process of transposition into the structure of another language (for example, aspectual forms of the verb, established constructions of the imperative or conditional mood, modal verbs and their equivalents, combinability of verbs

with certain prepositions, features of the subjunctive mood, etc.). All this provokes errors in the use and selection of forms in other language and to a certain extent complicates its mastery.

However, interference is not always negative. influence, in some cases the similarity of forms between native and in a foreign language there is still some grammatical categories coincide. At the lexical level this is manifested in the fact that most languages of the world have a common origin, and languages of the same groups are similar, so they contain a significant number of quantity of common words, i.e. in both languages they are pronounced the same or similar and mean the same unit. Most often, the vocabulary of a specific topic is common topics, such as science, music, study, theater, technology, sports, architecture and other professional topics. Comparing stable layers of vocabulary these languages, we can easily find pairs of words that not only have in common origin, but also to some extent retained a similar phonetic appearance. For example: Teeth-tish, candle-qandil, boy-bola (o'g'il), band-banda.

Based on the analysis, we can conclude that the stable these features and norms in the lexical and grammatical structure of the native language are always unconsciously transferred to similar systems of a non-native language, which is actively happening between the studied pair of languages - Uzbek- English, Uzbek tongue. Interference and similarity between these languages can be positive, simplifying promoting the mastery of a foreign language and conducting comparative studies, but more often has negative in nature, which provokes errors and the overlap of two personal language systems. To identify these difficulties and develop ways to overcome interference, it is necessary to develop a system when constant explanation and drawing parallels with the native language.

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